

SYNTHESIS REPORT

LA PIETRAIA: A CHANGING NEIGHBOURHOOD

Insights from a pilot intervention at the neighbourhood primary school to address the impacts of drought, heatwaves, and flash floods.

KEY POINTS

- The report focuses on the adaptation measures carried out in the *La Pietraia* neighbourhood. It is based on the results obtained by **eleven semi-structured interviews** and has the objective of capturing **stakeholders' beliefs and perspectives on climate change impacts** and on **adaptation actions** focusing on a **pilot intervention** at the neighbourhood primary **school complex**.
- **Droughts, heatwaves and flash floods** are affecting **people's daily life** in *La Pietraia*, particularly impacting **certain population groups** and **specific areas** of the neighbourhood. These effects are also connected to the city's structure. **Heatwave** effects are **aggravated** by the **lack of green spaces, street trees, and shading areas**.
- Interviewees highlight the need to **create a greener and cooler neighbourhood** that is able to **prevent the effects of flooding and heatwaves**. They advocate for interventions to be **co-designed** with the population and effectively **communicated**.
- **Floods and heatwaves** have significant **impacts** also in the primary **school complex**, and the interventions in the outdoor spaces of the school are expected to create three main positive effects: **improvement of school spaces, educational opportunities for children**, and the **dissemination of positive impacts** across the neighbourhood.
- Signals of the intervention's **success** in the **long run** are a greater **use of the school's outdoor spaces** and the **project replication** in other areas of the neighbourhood. Signals of success in the **short run** consist of its actual **implementation and maintenance**.
- According to interviewees, the pilot intervention does not carry any significant downside and has the potential to generate **several positive impacts** that could also extend beyond the school community, creating an **effective climate adaptation strategy for the entire neighbourhood**.

INTRODUCTION

This report analyses the results obtained from eleven interviews with local stakeholders focused on climate change decision-making in the Alghero neighbourhood of *La Pietraia*. The **interviews** aimed to **capture stakeholders' beliefs, perspectives, and perceptions on climate change impacts**, focusing on heatwaves, flash floods, and droughts, **as well as on adaptation actions and strategies implemented or planned** in the neighbourhood and the city of Alghero more broadly. The work leading to this report is part of the European Research Council-funded project [IMAGINE Adaptation](#), which explores new ways to evaluate and learn from adaptation actions and strategies in urban areas.

The present study focuses on the measures carried out as part of the Interreg Project ADAPTWISE in the neighbourhood of *La Pietraia*, in Alghero. ADAPTWISE includes a range of activities designed to tackle climate change impacts in the city, starting from the design and implementation of a **pilot action** aimed at **improving the outdoor spaces of the La Pedrera primary school**, through tree planting, the establishment of a rain garden, and the implementation of several green infrastructures.

The stakeholder mapping process was conducted by IMAGINE Adaptation's members with the support of other local partners: the Municipality of Alghero, ANCI Toscana, and the association for social promotion Anemone. The results presented here are based on **eleven semi-structured interviews** conducted engaging several local actors, including the primary school teachers and teachers from other schools in the neighbourhood, students' parents, intervention planners, municipal representatives, and members of neighbourhood civil society. These stakeholders were then divided into **two main groups**: a **broader group** consisting of four respondents not directly involved in the pilot action that were chosen for their involvement in the local civil society and environmental education initiatives, and a **group directly involved in the pilot intervention** composed of seven respondents who are, in various ways, connected to its implementation. Each interviewee was asked to provide their views on climate change impacts in Alghero and in the neighbourhood of *La Pietraia*. Then, for the broader stakeholder group, the questions focused on their needs and expectations about climate change adaptation measures in the city, while the intervention-related

group members were asked to provide their opinions on the initiative itself.

The remainder of this document contains the summary of the interviews, and it is structured as follows: the first section is dedicated to climate change impacts in the city and the neighbourhood and the needs connected to the realisation of climate change adaptation actions and strategies; the second section focuses on the pilot intervention actions to understand imaginaries, needs, and benefits arising from its design and implementation.

IMAGINING LA PIETRAIA ADAPTING TO CLIMATE CHANGE: PRESENT IMPACTS AND FUTURE PERSPECTIVES

Droughts, heatwaves, and flash floods are affecting people's lives in Alghero and *La Pietraia* in several ways. The 2025 **drought** conditions in the area are having concrete effects on the population, with **irrigation restrictions** that are being implemented for several agricultural productions. Drier conditions are also associated with the **rise in vegetable prices** and the **absence** of some **typical agricultural products** in the local markets. Moreover, the neighbourhood struggles with the heat island effect that affects people's health and aggravates the effects of **heatwaves**, forcing inhabitants to **stay indoors** and rely on **air conditioning**, which was not as commonly used in the past. **Floods** are also quite **frequent** in the area, affecting specific streets, particularly those located in the *Lido* area, which is the part of the neighbourhood closest to the coast.

As interviewees emphasised, flood impacts and heatwaves in the neighbourhood are **strictly connected to its structure**.

As for flooding, critical aspects involve the fragmented way in which the neighbourhood was built, the impermeability of the soils, as well as an old sewer system. These factors altogether aggravate the natural rainwater accumulation conditions that derive from the orography of the territory, as explained by an interviewee:

"When the rain arrives, it finds a completely waterproofed area upstream and the routes of descent of this water to the sea in the end are reduced to being two main roads. And yet, when you arrive in the tourist district (the lido area), you have a total blockage of the natural routes of water flow due precisely to how the houses have been built" [...] "If a few drops of rain fall in the summer, if a normal storm comes, the beach floods, that is, it floods regularly every time it rains."

Regarding heatwaves and heat islands, many respondents indicated that their effects are aggravated by the **absence of shading areas, green spaces, and trees** in the neighbourhood.

Even though all residents perceive flooding and heatwave impacts, certain population groups are especially affected. **Older adults, children, tourists, outdoor workers, and people with chronic illnesses** are identified by interviewees as the most impacted individuals. Climate change effects also raise equity concerns, particularly regarding people with limited financial means and those who live in the most densely populated areas. Moreover, these effects are most perceived in specific parts of the city, in some critical infrastructures, such as **the hospital located on the seafront and the schools in the neighbourhood, as well as in public spaces like playgrounds and main roads.**

Despite the consequences climate impacts are causing on people's daily lives in the area, results from the interviews highlight that **awareness** of climate change among the population is **limited**, with difficulties in connecting these impacts with structural problems. While this view is shared by all interviewees, they have different visions on its possible causes and the role that could be played by generational aspects. However, as emerged during one interview, the city's high average age of residents could offer interesting insights into both the population's vulnerability and its capacity for innovation. A partial awareness among the population is closely linked to engagement issues from past projects, possibly resulting from a gap between people's expectations and the way those projects were carried out; however, some interviewees noted that awareness is gradually increasing thanks to previous initiatives carried out in the neighbourhood.

The above **calls for the implementation of comprehensive adaptation actions and strategies** in order to co-create and design a **greener and cooler neighbourhood**. According to interviewees, the priority should be

acting on microclimates to create a **liveable city** where people can comfortably use outdoor spaces even during the summer months, as well as **preventing flooding** in the most affected areas. Interviewees pointed out that specific actions against heat waves could consist of **creating more green spaces, better maintaining existing ones, and improving tree planting in the streets** of the neighbourhood, focusing on the busiest axes, such as Via Don Minzoni, and in specific critical infrastructures, such as the civil hospital. Tree planting, in their view, is therefore a crucial measure to combat heatwaves, and in this regard, progress is being made as the municipality has recently planted new trees along some streets. It is also a matter of tree selection: in many streets, palm trees were planted, which might not adequately address the identified needs since they don't provide shade and are vulnerable to invasive species. As highlighted by one interviewee:

"... the main street had palm trees, several of them, but then a few years ago, with the arrival of the red palm weevil in Sardinia, there was a real die-off of palm trees. So, our entire avenue, Via Don Minzoni, which is the neighbourhood's main street, is left bare of trees. Now the administration [...] is replacing those palm trees with other trees, which, however, are still small at the moment."

As for flooding, interviewees highlight the need for the implementation of specific actions, such as **rain garden creation**, particularly in areas with impermeable pavement and, in particular, in the *Lido* area, which severely suffers from flooding problems:

"A rain garden along the sea is essential because when there's, say, a very severe flood, cars can't get through there; you have to take another road to get to Alghero."

These interventions, overall, could present an opportunity for the neighbourhood to reflect on its environmental continuity and create a green corridor. Moreover, interviewees stressed the need to **prioritise the most affected** social groups to address the equity issues arising from climate change impacts, and also **consider individuals who could be negatively impacted by their implementation**. Lastly, to maximise the impact of future adaptation projects, crucial aspects, according to the interviewees, concern the **co-design of the interventions with the population** and the **effective communication** of the obtained outcomes.

Figure 1 – La Pedrera Schoolyard. Source: <https://www.istitutocomprendivo2alghero.edu.it/>

BENEFITS, NEEDS, AND EXPECTATIONS FROM THE PILOT ACTION: VOICES FROM LA PEDRERA SCHOOL COMPLEX'S PROJECT

According to the second group interviewed, heatwaves and flash floods have a significant impact on the *La Pedrera* primary school complex, severely affecting both its buildings and outdoor spaces. **Flooding risks** are concentrated in the via Malta entrance, where water and mud accumulate during rainfall events. The school is also affected by **excessive heat in both its indoor and outdoor spaces**. As emerged during the interviews with the project planners, a thermal detection in mid-September revealed that in some areas of the school complex temperatures above 50°C were registered, and the teachers interviewed reported difficulties for students to attend classes due to excessive internal temperatures. As reported by the teachers during an interview:

"At our school, even a little water is enough to make the entrance from Via Malta impossible"; "We have gone from, let's say, spring to summer in a few days, so working in the classroom is truly a problem. We really need to open the windows, let fresh air in, which isn't there."

The pilot intervention aims to realize several interventions in the outdoor spaces of the school by planting various trees and a perimetral hedge, creating green infrastructures to protect the building from excessive heat

deriving from sun exposure, building a rain garden, and designing a winter vegetable garden, as well as organizing meetings and workshops for codesigning these actions with the students.

This set of measures has several benefits, which can be summarized into three main positive effects: **school improvement, educational opportunities, and the creation of a new space that could bring benefits to the entire neighbourhood.**

In terms of **school improvement**, respondents highlight that the intervention will renovate the school's outdoor spaces, creating more green and shaded areas, increasing biodiversity, and enhancing thermal comfort in the classrooms by reducing internal temperatures. Moreover, the construction of a rain garden will attenuate the flooding problems at the Via Malta entrance. As pointed out during one interview, these combined actions could make the school more attractive to parents seeking enrolment for their children.

Educational benefits were highlighted by most of the interviewees. Firstly, the school intervention provides an opportunity to raise students' awareness about the effects of climate change and the actions they can take to protect the environment, while also encouraging reflection on potential solutions. Secondly, the renovated outdoor spaces could be used for educational activities and open-air classes, which may be especially beneficial for neurodivergent and vulnerable children. Lastly, this initiative also has a value from a symbolic point of view, as noted by a respondent:

"I hope this wonderful project comes to fruition and that in 30 years, students who may become parents will be able to say: "I took part too! I was there!"

Interviewees also added that the intervention could be part of the **neighbourhood rebranding process** by creating a green lung in *La Pietraia* that could be enjoyed not only by students and the school population but also by the local community. The primary beneficiaries of the project are the children and the school members; however, many respondents highlighted the positive ripple effects of opening these spaces to others as well, creating a new space for everyone in the neighbourhood:

"...let it become a place for children to play, to play in the shade, maybe even outside of school activities, maybe something public, maybe financed with a European project. It could also be open in the afternoon, who knows, so people or children can go in there to play in the afternoon ...".

These benefits are linked to imagined changes in the future settings and uses of the school spaces. **Signals of the intervention's success** include **greater use of the school's outdoor spaces** for both educational and recreational activities, as well as the **project's replication** in several spaces of the neighbourhood, including other schools. Notably, for many stakeholders, the intervention's success is primarily associated with its effective implementation and short- to medium-term maintenance, identified as the main critical factors, rather than with its long-term benefits. To better manage the aspects connected to the initial phases of the intervention a crucial aspect involves ensuring a clear and appropriate allocation of responsibilities related to intervention involvement, execution, and, more importantly, the ongoing maintenance tasks, as indicated by one interviewee:

"I also think about the implementation itself, because unfortunately, we're used to many beautiful words, so many great projects that then don't materialize. In fact, when I participated, I said, "Let's hope, let's hope it actually gets done, that it gets implemented," because otherwise it would also be a huge disappointment for the children, especially because we've dedicated so many hours to it—the classes have been involved for so many hours—so it would be a shame, not only for them (the classes involved in the project), but also for those who will arrive".

It is also important to consider whether the intervention could negatively impact some categories. The prevailing view among stakeholders is that the intervention carries **no potential negative impacts**, aside from temporary inconveniences during the implementation phase, such as construction work lasting several days, and the ongoing effort required for its long-term maintenance. One respondent also considered that **asthmatic and allergic people** or people and students who are unfamiliar with nature could be negatively impacted. To minimize these downside impacts, specific indoor spaces could be created for these groups during critical times of the year, complemented by educational activities focused on the benefits of a more biodiverse space. The lack of significant downsides is also reflected in the community's enthusiasm: when planners discussed the intervention with residents during some informal occasions, they appeared genuinely excited about it.

Overall, according to the interviewees, the pilot intervention in *La Pietraia* primary school complex has the potential to generate several positive impacts that could also extend beyond the school community and reach a broader population, creating an effective climate adaptation strategy for the entire neighbourhood.

CONCLUSIONS

The results that emerged from this study offer interesting information about **how climate change is affecting *La Pietraia* and how the local population is experiencing and perceiving it**. Through identifying the key impacts and the most vulnerable categories and areas, this work could serve as a suggested indication for planning the next adaptation measures in the neighbourhood, as well as provide insights on specific actions that should be implemented and ensure that adaptation actions and strategies in the neighbourhood result in effective outcomes for its inhabitants.

As for the pilot intervention in *La Pedrera* school complex, whose activities started during the school year 2024–2025, this report summarizes the needs and expectations, as well as the most critical aspects, that should be considered for the next phases of the initiative. The interviews with those who experience the school spaces daily highlight an urgent need to implement this intervention. The proposed pilot action has the potential to enhance their everyday life while addressing the impacts of droughts, flash floods, and heatwaves within the school, and a crucial aspect is also connected to an effective communication of the long-term cascading benefits on the entire neighbourhood. If properly managed, executed, and communicated, the schoolyard intervention could trigger a virtuous cycle of actions and strategies, leading to the tangible realization of the community's imaginaries for adapting *La Pietraia* more effectively to climate change.

CREDITS

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